

Iterative Learning Controller for Tendon-Driven Continuum Soft Robots

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Abstract—To exploit soft robots’ versatility, the control problem must be tackled. The main challenges depend on the continuum dynamics and the need to use a feedforward control action. To solve this challenge, this work proposes a feedforward iterative learning controller. The algorithm updates the torque action by means of both the model and data from past trials. Then, we test the proposed controller via experiments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thanks to their deformable, compliant, and continuous bodies [1], soft robots may also represent an extension tool embedded in classic rigid counterparts e.g., end effector [2] or limbs [3]. However, the control problem has many open challenges [4]. Two are the main control approaches: feedforward learning-based [5]–[7] or feedback model-based [4], [8], [9]. The former ensures stiffness preservation, but it is time-expensive. On the other hand, the latter achieves high performance stiffening the robot’s behavior [10] and needing a precise robot model. Hence, we report a special case of

Fig. 1. Control scheme of iterative learning controller for continuum robots.

the computed torque-like iterative learning controller (ILC)

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feedforward strategy presented in [11] Fig. 1. The algorithm combines learning-based and model-based components. The controller uses the Lagrangian description [12] and data from precedent trials. ILCs deal with soft continuum robots in [13] and [11]. The former uses a feedback law that stiffens up the robot’s behavior. The latter represents the general case w.r.t. the ones presented in this work.

Finally, we tested the algorithm via experiments with varying trajectories.

II. MODEL OF SOFT CONTINUUM ROBOTS

We report a model for soft continuum arms.

Fig. 2. Scheme of a soft continuum arm with configuration $q = [\phi, \theta, \delta L]$.

a) *Kinematics*: Considering the i -th segment in Fig. 2 $i = 0, \dots$, we model the curvature using the classic PCC approach, i.e., $q_i = [\phi_i, \theta_i, \delta L_i]^T \in \mathcal{X}^3, \forall i$. Based on Fig. 2, we write the kinematics $T_i^s(q_i, s) \in \mathcal{X}^{4 \times 4}, s \in [0, 1]$, i.e., [11]

$$T_i^s(q_i, s) = \begin{bmatrix} R_z(\phi_i)R_y(\theta_i s)R_z(-\phi_i) & R_z(\phi_i)R_y(\theta_i s)p_i(q_i) \\ 0_{1 \times 3} & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

with $p_i(q_i) = [0, 0, L_i + \delta L_i]^T \in \mathcal{X}^3$ and $R_{(\cdot)} \in SO(3)$.

Following [14], we derive the differential kinematics, i.e., $\dot{\xi}_i = J_i(q)\dot{q}_i, \forall i$ where $\xi_i \in \mathcal{X}^6$ collects the tip velocities, and the Jacobian $J_i \in \mathcal{X}^{6 \times n}$, where $f_{K_i}(\cdot, \cdot) : \mathcal{X}^3 \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^6$ is the kinematics map.

b) *Lagrangian Dynamics*: Using the classical Lagrangian approach [12], one has

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + l(q, \dot{q}) = P(q)u, \quad (2)$$

where $\ddot{q} \in \mathcal{X}^n$ includes the accelerations. $M(q) \in \mathcal{X}^{n \times n}$ is the symmetric inertia matrix. $l(q, \dot{q}) \triangleq C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) + D\dot{q} + Kq$ where $C(q, \dot{q}) \in \mathcal{X}^{n \times n}$ is the Coriolis matrix, $D, K \in \mathcal{X}^{n \times n}, D, K \succ 0$ are the damping and stiffness matrices. $u(\cdot) : [0, t_f] \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^m$ is the controller, and $P(q) \in \mathcal{X}^{n \times m}$ is the actuation matrix such as $\text{rank}\{P(q)\} \leq p$, i.e., $p \leq m \leq n$.

Finally, we define the output $y(\cdot) \in \mathcal{X}^p$ and its function $h(\cdot) : [0, t_f] \times \mathcal{X}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^p$, i.e.,

$$y = h(q(t)) = q, \quad \|\partial h(q)/\partial q\| = \|I_3\| \leq h_0 \in \mathcal{X}. \quad (3)$$

Recalling (2), one has what follows.

Property 1. For any soft robots (2) $\forall q, \dot{q} \in \mathcal{X}^n$, there exist positive constants (see, e.g., [4], [11], [12]): $0 < b_m \leq \|M(q)\| \leq b_M$, $\|C(q, \dot{q})\| \leq b_C(\|\dot{q}\| + \|q\|)$, $\|G(q)\| \leq b_G\|q\|$, and $0 < \|P(q)\| \leq b_P$.

Leveraging Property 1, we remark what follows.

Remark 1. The term $l(\cdot) : \mathcal{X}^n \times \mathcal{X}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^n$, $l(\cdot) \in \mathcal{K}_\infty$ and it is such that $\|l(q, \dot{q})\| \leq b_l(\|q\|, \|\dot{q}\|)(\|q\| + \|\dot{q}\|)$, with $b_l(\|q\|, \|\dot{q}\|) = \|K\| + b_C(\|\dot{q}\| + \|q\|) + b_G\|q\|$.

Therefore, the soft robots' dynamic is locally Lipschitz. It is instrumental to assume what follows.

Assumption 1. The system (2)-(3) is inertially coupled.

Assumption 1 guarantees that the system's relative degree is $r = 2 \forall q, \dot{q} \in \mathcal{X}^n$ (see, e.g., [11], [15]).

Assumption 2. Let $y_d(\cdot) : [0, t_f] \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^p$ be the desired output. We assume $y_d(\cdot)$ to be feasible for (2)-(3).

Assumption 2 certifies existence of the unique desired state and bounded controller, i.e., the control problem solution [15].

Property 2. Soft robots are Input to State Stable [11].

III. ITERATIVE LEARNING CONTROL DESIGN

We here present the control approach also dealing with locally Lipschitz nonlinearities [11].

Lemma 1. Consider (2), Assumption 1, 2, and Property 2. Let $f(\cdot) : \mathcal{X}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^n$ be one of all the terms in (2)-(3), $\exists f_0(\|z\|) \in \mathcal{K}_\infty$ and $b_f \in \mathcal{X}^+$ finite such that

$$\|f(z_1) - f(z_2)\| \leq f_0(\|z\|)\|z_1 - z_2\| \leq b_f\|z_1 - z_2\|. \quad (4)$$

Recalling (2), we define the following iterative learning rule

$$u_{j+1}(t) = (I_m - b_M \zeta P^+(q_j) M^{-1}(q_j) P(q_j)) u_j(t) + M^{-1}(q_j) l(q_j, \dot{q}_j) + \Upsilon_P (y_d - y_j) + \Upsilon_V (\dot{y}_d - \dot{y}_j) + \ddot{y}_d, \quad (5)$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots$ is the iteration, $\zeta \in (0, 1)$, $\Upsilon_P, \Upsilon_V > 0$ are the gains. The initial guess, i.e., $j = 0$, can be selected as

$$u_0(t) = P^+(q_d) (M(q_d) \ddot{y}_d + l(q_d, \dot{q}_d)), \quad (6)$$

or a constant torque, e.g., $u_0(t) \equiv \bar{u}$. We highlight that (5) is feedforward, thus it secures the robot's stiffness [10]. The error $e_j(t) \in \mathcal{X}^p$ is

$$e_j(t) \triangleq q_d(t) - q_j(t). \quad (7)$$

In Theorem 1, we show the controller (5)'s convergence.

Theorem 1. Let us consider (2)-(3), Property 1, and Assumptions 1-2. Let (5) be the control law and (7) the error. Then

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow +\infty} \|e_j(t)\|_\lambda \rightarrow 0. \quad (8)$$

Proof. Recalling (5), one has

$$u_{j+1} = (I_m - b_M \zeta P^+(q_j) M^{-1}(q_j) P(q_j)) u_j + \Upsilon_V \dot{e}_j + \Upsilon_P e_j + M^{-1}(q_j) l(q_j, \dot{q}_j) - M^{-1}(q_d) l(q_d, \dot{q}_d) + M^{-1}(q_d) P(q_d) u_d. \quad (9)$$

From (9), one can write

$$\|\delta u_{j+1}\| \leq \varphi \|\delta u_j\| + b (\|\delta q_j\| + \|\delta \dot{q}_j\|) + \|M^{-1}(q_d) P(q_d) - \zeta b_M P^+(q_j) M^{-1}(q_j) P(q_j)\| \|u_d\| + \|M^{-1}(q_j) l(q_j, \dot{q}_j) - M^{-1}(q_d) l(q_d, \dot{q}_d)\|, \quad (10)$$

with $\delta u_{j+1} \triangleq u_j - u_d$ and $b = \max\{\|\Upsilon_V\|, \|\Upsilon_P\|\}$. Noting that $\varphi < 1$, and recalling Property 1, and Lemma 1 lead to

$$\|\delta u_{j+1}\| \leq \varphi \|\delta u_j\| + \bar{b} (\|\delta q_j\| + \|\delta \dot{q}_j\|), \quad (11)$$

where $\bar{b} \triangleq b_\varphi b_{u_d} + \frac{b_l}{b_M} + b$ with $b_\varphi \in \mathcal{X}^+$ derives from (Lipschitz) $\|M^{-1}(q_d) P(q_d) - \zeta b_M P^+(q_j) M^{-1}(q_j) P(q_j)\|$. Leveraging Gronwall-like Lemma [11] and λ -norm properties lead to $\|\delta \dot{q}\|_\lambda \leq b_q \|\delta u\|_\lambda$ and $\|\delta \dot{q}\|_\lambda \leq b_{\dot{q}} \|\delta u\|_\lambda$ with $b_q, b_{\dot{q}} < 1$. Thus, one has

$$\|\delta u_{j+1}\|_\lambda \leq (\varphi + \bar{b}(b_q + b_{\dot{q}})) \|\delta u_j\|_\lambda \triangleq \bar{\varphi} \|\delta u_j\|_\lambda.$$

Due to continuity property, $\exists \lambda > 0$ such that $\bar{\varphi} < 1$. Hence, substituting the first j trials when j goes to infinity holds $\lim_{j \rightarrow +\infty} \bar{\varphi}^j \|\delta u_0\|_\lambda = 0$. Leveraging (7) leads to (8). This concludes the proof. \square

Note that (5) uses a bound of $M(q)$. However, it exploits the knowledge of the model speeding up the learning.

IV. VALIDATION

We test the controller (5) performance with varying trajectories on hardware [3]. All unities are expressed in the MSK.

We employ the control law (5), and the control gains are $K_P = 5$ and $K_V = 0.1$. We model the soft robot with one segment and the $\text{rank}\{P(q)\} = 3, \forall q \in \mathcal{X}^n$, i.e., $p = 3$.

a) *Actuation Matrix:* From (2), we model $P(q) \in \mathcal{X}^{n \times m}$, [14]. Considering tendons Figs 2 and 3. The matrix is $P(q) = [P_1(q), \dots, P_m(q)]$ with $P_k(q) \in \mathcal{X}^n, k \in [1, m]$. From Figs 2-3, the k -th tendon acts in $p_{T_k} \in \mathcal{X}^3$ with pure force, i.e., (local frame) $f_k = [0, 0, -u_k]^\top$. For each k , one has

$$P_k(q) = \partial J_{p_{T_k}}^\top(q) f_k / \partial u_k, \quad (12)$$

with $J_{p_{T_k}}^\top(q) = J_p^\top(q) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial q} R_k(q) p_{T_k}\right)^\top$ and $J_p p_{T_k}(q) \in \mathcal{X}^{3 \times n}$.

Fig. 3. Experimental Platform [3], [11].

Fig. 4. Experiments results for Exp #1 in (a)-(b) and Exp #2 in (c)-(d).

Fig. 5. Photo-sequences of the Exp #1 final iteration.

The soft continuum robot has a silicon body Fig. 2 [3], and it is equipped with four Dynamixel motors acting via stainless steel tendons, and the IMU BNO055 [11].

IMU data are used to derive the PCC configuration via (1) [16]. Leveraging (5), the next torque control action is computed. The parameters are: $L = 0.098$, $I_{xx} = I_{yy} = 3e - 4$, $I_{zz} = 0$, $m = 1$, $\kappa = 5$, and $d = 1$ [3], [11].

The controller is tested via two trajectories: Exp #1 and #1. The desired trajectory are minimum jerks, with initial positions $\#1 y_0 = [-0.7, 0.1, 0]^T$ and $\#2 y_0 = [-\pi/2, 0.07, 0]^T$, while the finals are $\#1 y_f = [-\pi/2, 0.7, 3e - 3]^T$ and $\#2 y_f = [0.3, 0.7, 2e - 3]^T$, and the final time is $t_f = 15$ and $5s$.

Fig. 4 reports the results for Exp #2 and #3. Fig.s 4(a),4(c) show error evolution over iteration, Fig.4(b),4(d) depict the output performances. Finally, Fig.s 5-6 depict photo-sequences of the last iteration of the two tests.

A. Discussion

Results show good tracking performance Fig.s 4(b) and 4(d) while performing good deformations managing different velocities (Fig.s 5, and 6).

Fig. 6. Photo-sequences of the Exp #2 final iteration.

Thanks to the learning the system does not move at the first iteration and it completes the task after a few Fig.s 5 and 6.

Finally, since the controller (5) is feedforward, it does not modify the system elasticity.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed an iterative control algorithm for the continuum robots class. The controller is purely feedforward. Hence, it preserves the soft robots' elasticity. Finally, the approach's effectiveness is tested on real hardware varying tasks. Future work will generalize the iterative learning control by introducing machine learning approaches.

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